

EVIDENCE REPORT

In response to the EU Call for Evidence for Initiative: 2026-2030 Gender Equality Strategy

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CITATION:

Kulpa, R. and Zabrzewska, A. (2025) *Evidence Report (Poland). In response to the EU Call for Evidence for an Initiative: 2026-2030 Gender Equality Strategy.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15823668>

COUNTRY FOCUS:

Poland

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Introduction

This Evidence Report focuses on 2026-2030 Gender Equality Strategy and provides evidence of its importance and the necessity to uphold it, by drawing on the examples of Poland (and by extension, speaking to Central and Eastern European (CEE) region).

Poland's sociopolitical climate presents challenges to gender equality due to organised anti-feminist, anti-abortion, and anti-LGBTQ+ mobilisations, with the state directly contributing to restrictions on reproductive rights. 'Anti-gender' mobilisations undermine core human rights, exploiting bodily autonomy and gender and sexual freedoms as battlegrounds for patriarchal control.

Evidence from The RESIST Project, and from other data, strongly indicate a positive effect that the EU Gender Equality Strategy has had in the past and currently on ameliorating and enshrining equality in the Polish (and broader CEE) context. Therefore, it is crucial that the progressive direction taken by the EU in terms of gender equality rights is upheld and continued.

Conservative 'anti-gender' actors in Poland equate gender expression with 'gender ideology', LGBTIQ+ identities and experiences with 'homopropaganda' or 'LGBT agenda', and sex education with the 'sexualisation of children', presenting them as foreign Western imports that are a threat to the nation. **Anti-feminist, anti-LGBTIQ+, and anti-abortion actors position themselves as defenders of Polish ethnic and national identity, democracy, Catholic values, heteronormative family and marriage** ([RESIST Project Team, 2024a](#)). Resistance against 'anti-gender' politics is led predominantly by civil society organisations. Feminist and queer activists frequently face burnout and disillusionment due to a hostile environment and underfunding. However, strong community support and solidarity practices are cornerstones of resistance, and intersectional synergies between women's and LGBTIQ+ movements are emerging.

The RESIST Project's Report on Poland ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#)) shows that the constant need to navigate hostile sociopolitical environments and lack of adequate funding leads to burnout, apathy, disillusionment, and disbelief in social change among activists working towards gender equality. There are clear negative impacts on the mental health and wellbeing of women and LGBTIQ+ persons, who are the main target of 'anti-gender' politics. People who are multiply marginalised and minoritised due to their intersectional positionalities are usually more adversely affected.

Despite challenges and attacks, the struggle for gender equality in Poland is fuelled by **strong ethos of community support, mutual care, and solidarity practices**. These positive experiences are clearly pronounced in the Polish context as a common way of coping with the pressures of 'anti-gender' politics.

The introduction of **Gender Equality Plans** (GEPs) in Polish institutions, including in higher education, has often been perceived by RESIST Project's participants as a **facade policy, implemented primarily for legal compliance rather than to advance genuine gender equality**. Despite this, pro-feminist and pro-LGBTIQ+ individuals within these institutions continue to make efforts to use these superficial policies to raise awareness about issues such as gender-based violence.

Participants emphasized that despite instances of political and religious interference in higher education institutions (HEI), EU policies on equality and diversity in education and research remain crucial, serving as tools to combat transphobia, anti-feminism, xenophobia, racism, and homophobia in higher education.

RESIST research participants noted some unintended effects of ‘anti-gender’ mobilisations that contributed to an **increase in social awareness around issues related to abortion and LGBTIQ+ rights in Poland**. These ‘ricochet effects’ (occurring whenever a mal-intended ‘anti-gender’ tactic has an unexpected side effect beneficial to queer-feminist resistance) are perceived as resulting in greater self-organisation, volunteering, and grassroots community-building initiatives among younger generations of adults ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#)).

Some of these ‘ricochet effects’ can be traced to the 2016 and 2020-2021 mass protests against changes in legislation on abortion and the Summer 2020 pro-LGBTIQ+ protests, which can be perceived as having “contributed to the awareness that **reproductive justice concerns not only cisgender heterosexual women and that the struggle for women’s rights and gender equality is closely and inherently connected to the struggle for LGBTIQ+ rights**” ([Zabrzewska and Dubrow, 2021](#)).

However, RESIST findings serve as a reminder that these emerging synergies between women’s rights, trans rights, sex workers’ rights, and LGBTIQ+ rights have not been fully or uniformly achieved, and these pro-equality movements are negatively impacted by internal divides ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#)). Helping to foster those synergies, alliances, and collaborations is crucial in effective resistance against ‘anti-gender’ politics.

Key takeaways

- 1) Women’s rights, reproductive rights, trans rights, and LGBTIQ+ rights are closely intertwined and intersectionally connected, and so are ‘anti-gender’ mobilisations against them. Fostering alliances and collaborations between various pro-equality movements is crucial for effective resistance against ‘anti-gender’ politics.
- 2) ‘Anti-gender’ mobilisations in Poland (driven by politicians, media, religious figures, as well as anti-feminist, anti-abortion, and anti-LGBTIQ+ organisations) pose a threat to the effective implementation of gender equality policies and reforms, actively stalling advancements.
- 3) Initiatives for women’s rights, LGBTIQ+ rights, reproductive rights, and safe abortion are primarily driven by non-governmental organisations and collectives. These groups face constant pressures to limit diversity-promoting, pro-abortion, LGBTIQ+-inclusive education and aid.
- 4) Feminist and queer activists and public intellectuals face discrimination, shortage of resources, and burnout induced by systemic factors (i.e. underfunding and the constant need to navigate hostile sociopolitical environments).
- 5) Gender-inclusive education in Poland is stunted by ‘anti-gender’ mobilisations, which frame any discussion of gender and sexuality as ‘gender ideology’ and ‘LGBT agenda’. Public institutions in Poland fail to adequately address the issues of gender and sexual diversity.

- 6) Gender Equality Plans require more robust implementation and assessment to secure institutional commitment and impact, rather than relying on the labour of individuals personally committed to gender equality.
- 7) Strengthening and promoting EU policies on equality and diversity in higher education is needed to effectively combat misogyny, sexism, anti-feminism, xenophobia, racism, transphobia and homophobia, as well as instances of political and religious interference in academic freedoms.
- 8) **The EU commitment and promotion of equal rights for all is of key importance to support civil society in enshrining gender equality into policy solutions, legal frameworks, political culture, and daily lives of women and LGBTIQ+ communities at local, regional, national, and international levels.**

Recommendations

- 1) **Recognise 'anti-gender' mobilisations as a systemic threat:** 'Anti-gender' mobilisations should be recognised as a component of democratic backsliding and disinformation that poses a threat to fundamental EU values. Utilise EU Rule of Law Mechanisms (e.g. Article 7 TEU procedures, Rule of Law Framework, Conditionality Regulation) to address systemic violations linked to 'anti-gender' policies.
- 2) **Embed intersectionality in gender equality strategies:** Ensure meaningful participation of lesbian, trans, intersex, racialised, disabled, migrant, and youth voices in strategy design, implementation, and monitoring.
- 3) **Strengthen Gender Equality Plans:** Sustain and reinforce GEPs in the 2026–2030 Gender Equality Strategy by expanding them into inclusive and intersectional schemes, supporting institutional implementation, ensuring investment in long-term capacity-building, implementing monitoring and evaluation frameworks, and promoting coordinated approaches among the Commission, Member States, RFOs and RPOs to secure institutional commitment and impact.
- 4) **Strengthen gender equality in HEI and R&I by enhancing gender balance in decision-making and combatting gender-based violence:** The Strategy should emphasize institutional change, focusing on gender balance in research teams, gender balance in decision-making, and the integration of gender dimensions in R&I. The 2026–2030 Strategy should also specifically tackle gender-based violence in HEI and R&I, prioritizing the implementation of the Zero Tolerance Code of Conduct and adopting the 7P model as a guiding framework. The European Commission and Member States should coordinate efforts to ensure institutional accountability and support for implementation. Additionally, protections for researchers at risk, especially LGBTIQ+ researchers on mobility schemes in hostile environments, must be strengthened.
- 5) **Ensure continuous and long-lasting impact, regardless of shifting political landscapes through international funding schemes:** Feminist and queer organisations in Poland working to create safe spaces for women and LGBTIQ+ people face underfunding and cannot rely on state support due to the prevailing anti-feminist and anti-LGBTIQ+ climate. This lack of resources hampers their ability to implement effective programs and initiatives. The 2026–2030 Gender Equality Strategy should acknowledge and address systemic barriers to gender equality and sexual diversity, including underfunding but also safety threats and limited access to decision makers.

- 6) **Promote comprehensive education on gender and sexual diversity combined with education on ‘anti-gender’ movements:** Raising awareness about gender and sexual diversity, as well as the manifestations, tactics, and effects of ‘anti-gender’ politics, is essential for fostering more educated and open societies. Educating people about the harmful effects of ‘anti-gender’ movements on gender and sexual diversity, and how these efforts affect individuals’ lives, can help foster understanding and acceptance.
- 7) **Strengthen legal and institutional protections:** Ensure effective and harmonised implementation of the Violence Against Women Directive, Victims’ Rights Directive, and EU anti-discrimination legislation, ensuring that LGBTIQ+ people in intersectional positions are included in the implementation processes.
- 8) **Regulate hate speech and hate crime:** Promote EU-wide minimum standards for defining and prosecuting hate crimes targeting LGBTIQ+ persons, aligned with the proposed inclusion of hate crime and hate speech in the list of EU crimes (Article 83 TFEU). Support EU-wide initiatives to promote journalistic ethics and counter disinformation, regulate online hate speech and ‘anti-gender’, anti-feminist, anti-LGBTIQ+ violence through existing digital and media legislation (e.g. Digital Services Act, Code of Practice on Disinformation).
- 9) **Address ‘anti-gender’ misinformation and hate speech by public officials and elected representatives:** Political accountability mechanisms at EU and national level are needed, especially within the European Parliament, to hold public figures accountable for using and promoting ‘anti-gender’ misinformation and hate speech aimed at women and LGBTIQ+ persons.

Explanation & Evidence

How do ‘anti-gender’ tactics manifest and why are they harmful?

Polish ‘anti-gender’ landscape, as examined by the EU-funded [RESIST Project](#), is both crucial and harmful to the situation of women, transgender persons, and the overall LGBTIQ+ community in Poland, impacting local policies and practices. This is because:

- a) ‘Anti-gender’ politics are used to deny women’s rights and autonomy. They seek to ensure that heteronormativity is reproduced in contextually specific ways to safeguard the social and gendered reproduction of the nation. They appropriate women’s bodily autonomy as a site of political and ideological contestation and patriarchal control. In the RESIST project, abortion was identified as a site to challenge women’s rights in the name of Christian and national values in the Polish, Hungarian, and European Parliaments. In these debates, cis-women’s bodies are framed as having too much agency in terms of choice to terminate a pregnancy or as needing paternalistic protection ([RESIST Project Team, 2024a](#)).
- b) ‘Anti-gender’ actors position themselves as defenders of Polish ethnic and national identity, Catholic values, and the traditional heteronormative family ([RESIST Project Team, 2024a](#)), implicitly treating women and children as instruments of national continuity rather than autonomous subjects capable of self-determination.
- c) ‘Anti-gender’ politics fosters panic around education on gender identity, sexual orientation, sexual health, and sexual relationships, portraying those educational efforts as dangers to the impressionable young adults ([RESIST Project Team, 2024b](#))

- d) 'Anti-gender' actors use the concept of 'sexualisation' to attack not only feminist critiques of gender roles, ineffective (sexual) education, and LGBTIQ+ activism but also the rights of transgender individuals to bodily autonomy and self-determination ([RESIST Project Team, 2024b](#)), ultimately hindering the progress of gender-inclusive education, leaving LGBTIQ+ people vulnerable to discrimination and marginalisation.

Findings from Poland and other case study contexts studied by the RESIST Project show that 'anti-gender' politics is constructed and promoted as a defence of democracy against 'gender ideology' that, in turn, is positioned as a threat to the nation and societies.

'Anti-gender' politics seeks to advance through creating divisions between presumptively homogeneous hetero/cis-normative nations and LGBTIQ+ people. Treating the LGBTIQ+ community as separate from and different to the nation and democracy is used to withdraw, mitigate and/or debate LGBTIQ+ rights. This provides a way of marginalising LGBTIQ+ people through discourses that frequently encompass conspiratorial elements and reconstitute 'democracy' as the modality through which the nation is reproduced ([RESIST Project Team, 2024a](#)). **This also adversely affects gender equality initiatives and opportunities for cisgender heterosexual women, who are restricted by 'anti-gender' politics to patriarchal and heteronormative roles.**

Nationalist tropes work to frame LGBTIQ+ inclusive curriculum content as foreign and external to the national project. In the European Union context, LGBTIQ+ families are used by 'anti-gender' parliamentarians to posit a threat to the right of individual member states to make rules for themselves. This is a particularly contentious issue threatening the cohesion of the European Union in a post-Brexit Europe ([RESIST Project Team, 2024a](#)).

What strategies do women and LGBTIQ+ persons in Poland use to resist 'anti-gender' movements and overcome institutional barriers to gender equality?

Findings from the RESIST Project's case study on Poland ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#)) show that pro-feminist and pro-LGBTIQ+ individuals actively engage in reusing and enhancing available resources to address the injustices faced by those who have been targets of discrimination or bullying. This is often a strategic choice directed against habituated, institutionalised bureaucracies.

For example, where Higher Education institutions have, in many cases, introduced **Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)** for legal compliance, and not for greater gender equality, pro-feminist, pro-LGBTIQ+ individuals operating within those institutions still make the effort to use these façade policies to raise awareness about e.g. gender-based violence and other important matters. In the words of one of the study's participants: **"They [university managers] don't take too much interest in us [case workers in the equality division] and because of that we can do what we feel is right and important."** ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#))

In other cases, some participants have taken legal or administrative action to counteract the effects of 'anti-gender' politics, including using formal complaint procedures. For example, on social media, people mentioned actively reporting users and content as discriminatory and harmful. In some instances, this has been escalated to reporting instances to the police, when anti-discrimination provisions in Polish law can be made use of in defence of one's own wellbeing. ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#))

The RESIST Project has gathered numerous examples of direct interference by political and religious figures in the functioning of higher education institutions (HEI) in Poland ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#)). Participants recounted that the effects of ‘anti-gender’ politics have been a permissive atmosphere for political extortion, unjustified influence, and intimidation at a structural-institutional level. **On the positive side, participants noted the importance of the EU policies on equality and diversity in education, and research, development and innovation (RDI) sectors.** Although not intended nor directed as counter measures to ‘anti-gender’ mobilisations, they nonetheless have a positive, buffer effect. These become concrete references and tools with which to fight against the effects of transphobia, anti-feminism, xenophobia and racism, or homophobia in HEIs.

Participants frequently talked about mutual care and solidarity, building and reinforcing relationships as a way of managing the pressures of dealing with ‘anti-gender’ politics. These concern micro- and meso-level practices: respectively, reinvesting individual attention to friendships and reinforcing community building practices of mutual care and support.

What is the role of grassroots resistance and intersectionality in the fight for reproductive rights in Poland?

Strict abortion laws in Poland have strained civil society organisations (CSOs) that facilitate access to safe abortion services. The reproductive rights protests of 2020-2021 raised social awareness, sparked public debate, and increased media coverage around safe abortion. These protests also aligned with LGBTIQ+ communities, following earlier pro-LGBTIQ+ demonstrations in the summer of 2020, fostering an intersectional understanding that reproductive rights affect not only cisgender and heterosexual women.

The 2020 ruling of the Polish Constitutional Tribunal has severely limited access to legal abortion, removing the most common legal reason for abortion in Poland, i.e. foetal abnormalities. Despite months of street protests, the legislation has not been revoked, and legal abortion remains limited to cases of rape and threat to the pregnant person’s life, with abortion access handled predominantly by civil society organisations and mutual aid groups.

The latest report from [Aborcja bez Granic \[Abortion without Borders\]](#); henceforth ABG] estimates that, among all abortions for which data is available, 95.4% were pharmacological abortions facilitated by ABG and 2.9% were procedures performed outside of Poland with ABG's assistance. **Only 1.7% of abortions in 2024 were conducted through the state-funded healthcare system, NFZ.** ABG supported 47,000 abortions, with the total cost of support amounting to over 2 million PLN. The youngest person that received abortion support from ABG was 12 years old.

The first attempt at limiting abortion rights by the state was made in 2016 but it was successfully halted by mass strikes known as the Black Protests (named after black clothing worn by the protesters). After the Tribunal ruling of 2020, the Strajk Kobiet [Women’s Strike] protests became a nationwide movement, growing from a few dozen participants at local rallies to hundreds of thousands of activists, primarily women, protesting against abortion restrictions in Poland ([Zabrzewska and Dubrow, 2021](#)). According to [ACLED](#) data (Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project), there were 985 such protests in 2020, with three involving instances of violence and 24 protests involving police intervention, with protesters detained by the police ([Zabrzewska and Dubrow, 2021](#)). As [Grabowska 2021](#) observes, the protests attracted the most people in the history of modern feminism in Poland and were characterised by significant intersectional synergies with

the LGBTIQ+ movement, destabilising hegemonic feminist narratives that framed reproductive rights as a women's cause. Indeed, pro-LGBTIQ+ protests were the first to occur in Poland in 2020 under Covid-19 restrictions, sparked by the arrest of the LGBTIQ+ activist Margot. This incident led to confrontations with the police and the subsequent arrest of 48 individuals.

As [Zabrzewska and Dubrow, 2021](#) point out, the August 2020 protests and the synergy between queer, feminist, and women's movements in October 2020 protests, "contributed to the awareness that reproductive justice concerns not only cisgender heterosexual women and that the struggle for women's rights and gender equality is closely and inherently connected to the struggle for LGBTIQ+ rights."

Participant insights from the RESIST Project

The RESIST case study participants also mentioned the 2016 and 2020-2021 protests as important catalysts of **cross-societal support for women's rights, LGBTIQ+ rights, and reproductive rights**. One participant said:

Even though there was a lot of [...] anti-gender stuff going on, which also de facto raises awareness a bit, am I right? Because there's a certain reaction to it, more people are interested [...] I don't know, when I think about how there was a big demonstration in August after the arrest of Margot [non-binary activist] somehow I can also see the effects of that ['anti-gender' politics], that more people understood what police violence is about, that these are the kinds of things that are starting to become a mainstream issue.

However, the participants also pointed to the challenges inherent in intersectional inclusion within feminist and queer movements, with the younger generation of activists—who side with intersectional, trans-inclusive, and sex-work inclusive feminism—expressing discontent with trans-exclusionary and sex-work-exclusionary stances among some self-identified feminists from the older generation ([Kulpa and Kania, 2024](#)). As another participant said:

[I am] increasingly observing with horror how in my own community, that is, the feminist one, there arise such internal, community policies, transphobic [...] policies, actions, attitudes, social positions directed against, for example, sex workers. [...] I observe how patriarchy enters our own heads and divides our own broadly defined women's movements.

This serves as a reminder that synergies between women's rights, trans rights, sex workers' rights, and LGBTIQ+ rights have not been fully or uniformly achieved and that these movements are negatively impacted not only by 'anti-gender' politics but also internal divides. This is also why helping to foster those synergies, alliances, and collaborations is crucial in effective resistance against 'anti-gender' mobilisations and in fostering gender equality.